

SATURATED SALT SOLUTION (SSS) EMBALMING: AN ALTERNATIVE APPROACH

¹Ankur Pandey, ¹S.A.V. Manikanta Sarma, ¹Akshat Kaushik, ²Abhinov Verma, ³Shriprakash Singh, ⁴Archana Pathak, ⁵M.M Farooqui

¹PhD Scholar, ²Assistant professor, ³Associate professor, ⁴Professor, ⁵Professor & Head, College of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry, U.P. Pt. Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Pashu Chikitsa Vigyan Vishwavidyalaya Evam Go-Anusandhan Sansthan (DUVASU), Mathura, Uttar Pradesh, India, 281001

ABSTRACT

Embalming is a crucial practice in veterinary anatomy for the preservation of animal cadavers, allowing extended study and dissection while preventing decomposition. Traditional embalming methods have relied heavily on formalin, a formaldehyde-based fixative known for its tissue preservation capabilities but also for its adverse health effects, including respiratory irritation and carcinogenicity. This study explores an alternative embalming technique using a saturated salt solution (SSS) as a non-toxic, cost-effective, and accessible fixative. The proposed method involves a sequence of vascular perfusion steps: initial flushing of blood vessels with a 0.9% saline solution, followed by continuous perfusion and recirculation of SSS over 6–8 hours. This technique avoids the need for refrigeration, maintains tissue pliability and natural consistency, and significantly reduces health risks to handlers. Moreover, the effectiveness of preservation varies with the route of vascular access, with deeper cannulation offering superior results for visceral organs. This method offers a promising alternative for veterinary anatomy teaching and research, promoting a safer and more sustainable approach to cadaver preservation.

KEYWORDS: Non-toxic fixative, Cadaver preservation, Vascular perfusion, Formalin alternative, Tissue preservation, Anatomical dissection

INTRODUCTION

Veterinary embalming is the art and science of preserving animal bodies after death using chemical agents. This process delays decomposition and allows cadavers to be used for extended periods, particularly for educational and research purposes. Embalming is among the earliest surgical practices in human history and has been performed in various cultures worldwide. In certain geographical regions, natural environmental conditions like extreme cold or dry heat have also contributed to the natural mummification of animal and human remains.

HISTORICAL BACKGROUND OF EMBALMING

The first documented embalming practices date back over 5,000 years in ancient Egypt, where the technique was deeply intertwined with religious beliefs in resurrection. The second significant period of embalming history emerged during the European Renaissance, when cadaver preservation became essential for anatomical study and scientific dissection. The third major development occurred in the modern era, starting around 1861 with the American Civil War. Embalming gained popularity as a means of preserving soldiers' bodies for transport back home. The practice proved especially useful for high-ranking officials whose remains were often displayed across multiple locations for memorial ceremonies. Over time, embalming evolved through research, innovation, and refinement,